

Cu-**CHA** zeolite-based catalysts for the selective catalytic reduction of NO_x in exhaust diesel gas: addressing the issue of **Sulfur Stability**

Deliverable 6.1 WP6

Creation of CHASS website

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European Industrial Doctorates

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The CHASS project

CHASS is an H2020-MSCA ITN-EID project which aims to educate four PhD students. The project targets deactivation of SCR catalysts for NO_x removal from diesel exhaust gases, with special focus on poisoning by SO₂ and exposures to high temperatures. The aim is to build models based on a fundamental chemical understanding of the catalysts, which can be applied in the development of future exhaust systems.

See <http://chass-itn-project.eu> for more information.

Project partners

(Coordinator, Academic, University of Torino)

(Academic, Chalmers University of Technology in Gothenburg)

(Industrial, Umicore Denmark ApS and Umicore AG & Co KG)

About this document

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides a general overview of progress made and objectives achieved related to the launch of the CHASS official website. It reflects the progress made and the objectives planned at the time of writing of this document. The document will also give an overview on how the launch of the website will contribute to the promotion and dissemination of the CHASS project to the public.

Possible modifications and improvements might be added in future to address any elements not emerged at this stage of the project yet. The website provides the main point of initial contact and information to the public and to other researchers. According to what is requested in WP6 (communication and dissemination), the website has been designed to be professional, responsive and intuitive and it is planned to be regularly maintained using contents of different nature (e.g. video clips, practical guides, white papers, banners, brochures, images and photos, etc.). It is intended to share both general content on the project, but also non- confidential deliverables (when these become available). Dissemination level of this deliverable is *public*.

2. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable is part of work package (WP) 6 “Communication, dissemination and exploitation”, which aims to ensure efficient communication and dissemination of the project results, spreading information to a whole range of stakeholder among the scientific community, the related industrial sectors, policy makers, and the general public. Purpose of this document is to report all activities related to the launch of the website intended to improve external communication about the project.

The CHASS website was designed to be the main vehicle for communicating and disseminating activities of the work. The CHASS website serves as a central point of entry to all public materials, such as public deliverables, reports, newsletters, informational dissemination material, presentations and promotional videos developed as part of the project. These contents will then be shared also through Social Media channels dedicated to the project such as Facebook, Instagram, Youtube, Twitter.

The site will be periodically updated with contents of different nature, so that all sort of activities related to CHASS could be visible online. The site will be openly accessible online since the 30th of November.

Target Audience

Aim of the CHASS website is to spread as widely as possible the research activities of CHASS to all interested stakeholder. The target is thought to be composed by:

- The general public, who may need a clear and efficient set of information about the project;
- An audience made of experts in the field, who may want a deeper information on the subject;
- Stakeholders of different nature with a certain level of decision-making power (policy makers, related industrial sectors management).

Methodology and objectives

Our aim was to create a modern and user-friendly website that could be the first reference for communication activities related to the project in the most efficient way as possible. With this goal in mind, we aimed at ensuring the following qualities to it:

- **Intuitiveness.** We wanted the website to be user-friendly and able to provide a high level of user-experience easiness. In order to do this, an intentional use of visuals aimed at channeling the message and the mission of CHASS has been mobilized.
- **Network-based.** We wanted the site to be a point of reference for all people and similar project involved with CHASS. For this reason reference to similar projects and organizations are available on the site.
- **Knowledge-sharing.** Regular update of scientific resources is ensured through the website.
- **Transparency.** Transparency is ensured through the website both on the scientific and administrative sides. From the scientific side, Open Data policy of CHASS as an ITN Project is implemented through a dedicated page on the website to the Zenodo Community of CHASS; from the administrative side, visibility of non-confidential deliverables related to CHASS will be maximised through a dedicated webpage. Both pages will be regularly updated.
- **People-orientation.** In order to ensure a more «human» perception of the project, reference to the team and to their specific point of view of the project will be stressed, through

publication of personal photos, contributions and declarations from the academic staff of CHASS.

- **Internationalization.** Particular attention has been also given to stress the European dimension of the project. The theme of Europe-making through knowledge and science sharing is particularly stressed in the communication of CHASS. The concepts of mobility and Internationalization of the project is stressed through the use of evoking visuals and of symbols (such as the EU flag or photos of historical monuments of the cities of the Beneficiary Partners).

3. WORK DONE AND CURRENT STATUS

The website <https://www.chass-itn-project.eu/> has been developed and launched November 30th 2021.

In order to guarantee an efficient result, the CHASS team resorted to a professional company based in Turin, named Eta beta SCS (<http://www.etabeta.it>), to develop the website.

The website status is completed and will be frequently updated in order to provide a sound overview of the activities related to the project.

4. WEBSITE DEVELOPMENT AND STRUCTURE

The website was developed and made public by November 30th, 2021. The following screenshots were selected to illustrate the website development status as of November 29th, 2021.

All sections of the website have the CHASS logo at the top and the acknowledgement of funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 R&I EC Programme. Details on CHASS Privacy Policy can be found at the footer of the website.

The CHASS project website is available at <https://www.chass-itn-project.eu/> and is managed by the Coordinator Beneficiary of the project (University of Turin; Supervisor: Professor G. Berlier). The CHASS website has a privacy policy which is in line with general data policy regulations (GDPR).

The site has been developed through Wordpress as CMS tool. Also content-sharing tools such as <https://wetransfer.com> have been mobilized in order to implement the realization of the website.

Publication of non-confidential deliverables will be part of update of the website. The website will be updated regularly, based on the communication and dissemination plan guidelines by WP6.

The website has been structured along the following main pages (in order):

“Home Page”

CHASS **iftm-project**

Overview ▾ Research ▾ Team ▾ Dissemination ▾ Outreach ▾ Info What's New

CHASS Cu-CHA zeolite-based catalysts for the Selective Catalytic Reduction of NOx in exhaust diesel gas: addressing the issue of Sulfur Stability

OUR MISSION

Training 4 young scientists for a NOx free diesel

The aim of the CHASS network is to educate 4 Early Stage Researchers (ESRs), in a doctoral training programme, aimed at a better understanding of Cu-zeolite based catalysts for the removal of NOx from diesel exhaust gases. The objective of the programme is to develop catalysts for NOx removal by technological implementation of fundamental atomistic knowledge (UN Sustainable Development Goals 7, 9).

The homepage has been thought to deliver a good amount of information about the project with easiness and efficiency. The goal of the project, the beneficiaries and the location of the project are well represented through an interplay of graphics and texts.

OUR PARTNERSHIP

Università degli studi di Torino	Chalmers Tekniska Högskola AB	Umicore AG&Co KG	Umicore Denmark ApS
<small>Department of Chemistry of University of Turin</small>	<small>Department of Physics at Chalmers University of Technology Competence Centre for Catalysts</small>	<small>Automotive Catalysts Division at Umicore AG&Co KG</small>	<small>Research & Technology Automotive Catalysts at Umicore Denmark ApS</small>

We're all throughout Europe: European Community building with MSCA

MSCA are the EU's flagship funding programme for doctoral education and postdoctoral training. They aim to foster career development and further training of researcher, promoting internationalization of research and innovation, creating an international community supporting mobility of scientists from not only within Europe but also across the globe.

“Overview”

The page is structured along the following sections:

- **Core Competences:**

The essence of the project is represented around 4 of its main core competences with the help of ad-hoc designed graphics.

- **Application Areas:**

This section explains the implications the project could offer once the scientific results will be available.

The Physical Chemistry group at the Department of Chemistry and inter-departmental **NSRF Research Centre** of University of Torino has a long-term internationally recognized expertise in the characterization of surfaces and interfaces, particularly in the field of heterogeneous catalysis by advanced spectroscopy. These include in-situ and operando-IR absorption (FTIR, Raman) and electronic ($X\text{-ray}$ absorption \rightarrow XAS \rightarrow and $X\text{-ray}$ VES) spectroscopies, complemented by microcalorimetric studies.

and heterogeneous catalysis. Chalmers hosts the **Swedish National Competence Centre for Catalysis (NCC)**. The focus in CHASS is on quantum mechanical **Density Functional Theory (DFT)** calculations to study the electronic structure and atomic geometries in Cu-zeolites relevant for $\text{NH}_3\text{-SCR}$, together with the evaluation of **thermodynamic stability and free energy reaction paths** by Monte-Carlo and molecular dynamics methods.

Hanau is Umicore's global catalysis research center with a focus on **automotive catalysis**, fuel cell catalyst and some catalysts for industrial processes. Dr Martin Votzmeier at Umicore is Professor at the **Technical University of Darmstadt**, where he leads the group reaction engineering of catalytic processes. One research focus of the group in Hanau is the **development and application of mechanistic kinetic catalyst models**. The research site in Hanau has extensive engine- and lab testing facilities and hosts the automotive applied technology department that is responsible for developing exhaust systems.

The expertise and facilities of **Umicore DK** include lab-scale activity measurements, catalyst aging and measurement of catalyst deactivation, characterization of reduction and adsorption properties, preparation of monolithic catalysts, and production technology. These data form the basis for models that

“Research”

The page is structured along the following sections:

- Objectives
- Action
- PhD Projects

Objectives

Innovation, Research, Entrepreneurship

The general objective of CHASS is to educate 4 Early Stage Researchers (ESR) candidates in the context of a doctoral training network with strong, multi-faceted emphasis on world leading research, industrial innovation and entrepreneurship. The programme will additionally generate knowledge to enhance the performance of Cu-zeolite materials for the abatement of NO_x by $\text{NH}_3\text{-SCR}$.

CHASS is divided into 8 Work Packages

“Team”

Built on PhDs, to add a more people-oriented touch to the site, photos and «quote» about the project

“Dissemination”

The page is structured along the following sections:

- **Publications**
- **Research Data**

In order to ensure the maximum level of transparency, a whole page on the website is dedicated to the dissemination of OpenData results produced by CHASS through Zenodo, in order to maximise public exposure of CHASS scientific contribution.

The data generated by the consortium is deposited on the CHASS community site at Zenodo.

zenodo

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Automotive Catalysts Division at Umicore

Umicore Denmark ApS
Research & Technology Automotive Catalysts at Umicore

“Outreach”

The page is structured along the following sections:

- Workshops
- Activities
- Network

“Info”

For ensuring the maximum level of transparency, a dedicated page on the website is dedicated to the publication of non confidential deliverable, in order to maximise public exposure of CHASS modalities of implementation. Also both open and closed opportunities will be published.

CHASS itn-project

Overview ▾ Research ▾ Team ▾ Dissemination ▾ Outreach ▾ Info What's New 🔍

Info

	Open opportunities	▾
	Closed opportunities	▾
	Public deliverables	▾

“What’s New”

In order to ensure a regular spreading of CHASS activities, the page will be constantly updated with the latest material such as upcoming meetings, participations in events, dissemination actions, conferences, publications, whitepapers, photos, etc.

The figure gives a representation of the “News” page with the earliest events that start to populate the project news list (here: the Kick Off Meeting held in Hanau November 25th)

5. REFERENCES

- [1] Grant Agreement NUMBER 955839— CHASS
- [2] <https://www.chass-itn-project.eu/>
- [3] WordPress content management system (CMS). Website: <https://wordpress.com>
- [4] <https://wetransfer.com>